

ACTIVE MEN WITH UNCONTROLLED HYPERTENSION DEMONSTRATE HIGHER GLOBAL HEART RATE VARIABILITY AND LOWER STRESS INDEX (HIGHER HEART RATE VARIABILITY AND LOWER STRESS INDEX IN UNCONTROLLED HYPERTENSIVE MEN)

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ABSTRACT

To evaluate the level of physical activity and cardiac autonomic modulation in men with uncontrolled systemic arterial hypertension living in rural areas. A cross-sectional study was conducted, with participants randomized into active and sedentary hypertensive groups. Anthropometric, hemodynamic, body composition, cardiac autonomic modulation, and physical activity level measurements were performed. A total of 16 male participants were analyzed (9 active hypertensive and 7 sedentary hypertensive). The main findings indicate greater heart rate variability and lower cardiovascular stress in the active group compared to the sedentary group. Additionally, a moderate negative correlation was identified, suggesting that higher heart rate variability, as observed in the SDNN, is associated with lower cardiovascular stress. A moderate positive correlation was also observed between abdominal circumference and diastolic blood pressure, indicating that an increase in abdominal circumference corresponds to higher diastolic blood pressure values. Active hypertensive men exhibit greater heart rate variability and lower cardiovascular stress compared to sedentary men. A moderate positive correlation was observed between abdominal circumference and diastolic blood pressure. Evaluate the level of physical activity and cardiac autonomic modulation in men with uncontrolled systemic arterial hypertension living in rural areas, as a way to encourage and contribute to local preventive medicine.

Keywords: Hypertension, heart rate variability, men, physical activity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Systemic arterial hypertension (SAH) is a clinical condition that affects blood vessels, arteries, and other components of the circulatory system, potentially exerting a negative impact on other structures of the human body (de Moraes & Diniz, 2023). This condition is defined by the World Health Organization, as a pathology responsible for the chronic elevation of blood pressure and blood vessel tension (Campbell et al., 2022).

This condition represents a significant risk factor for the development of cardiovascular diseases, which have recently been among the leading causes of mortality worldwide (Mills, Stefanescu, & He, 2020). The WHO estimates that more than 7.1 million deaths worldwide are associated with SAH annually, and approximately 600 million people live with the condition. Data from Brazil indicate that the disease affects around 36 million people in the country (Al-Makki et al., 2022), (Hunter, Chapman, & Dhaun, 2021).

In addition to the negative impacts mentioned above, there are many adverse effects resulting from SAH. Evidence shows that this condition largely develops due to interactions among complex vascular, neurogenic, hormonal, renal, and metabolic regulatory mechanisms. Frequently, a functional imbalance in the autonomic nervous system occurs, with sympathetic dominance, which can lead to harmful health effects (Maciorowska, Krzesiński, Wierzbowski, Uziębło-Życzkowska, & Gielerak, 2022).

The sympathetic component of the autonomic nervous system increases the contractile force of myocardial fibers, elevates heart rate, and causes vasoconstriction, factors that result in increased cardiac output and peripheral vascular resistance, while the parasympathetic component acts by inhibiting sympathetic activity. Blood pressure is determined by the product of cardiac output and peripheral vascular resistance. Therefore, it is suggested that the sympathetic branch contributes to the elevation of blood pressure, while the parasympathetic branch acts to reduce it (De Angelis, Santos, & Irigoyen, 2004; Pando, 2024).

There are several methods that allow for the direct and indirect evaluation of autonomic nervous system functions. One of them is the assessment of heart rate variability (HRV), a tool that can be recognized as the heart's response to any type of stimulus. Thus, its variation can be used as a warning sign for increased cardiovascular risk and heart diseases (Tiwari, Kumar, Malik, Raj, & Kumar, 2021).

Due to its high prevalence and the negative consequences of hypertension, additional approaches beyond pharmacological treatment are necessary for managing this condition, with physical exercise being one of the main interventions (Saco-Ledo, Valenzuela, Ruiz-Hurtado, Ruilope, & Lucia, 2020). Regular physical exercise is recommended not only for its benefit in reducing blood pressure but also for lowering cardiovascular morbidity and mortality in individuals with hypertension (Barroso et al., 2021), (Fu et al., 2020).

Thus, given the importance and relevance of this study in reinforcing findings about the influence of physical activity levels and cardiac autonomic modulation in men with SAH, while considering sociodemographic factors. Given the above, the objective of the study is to evaluate the level of physical activity and cardiac autonomic modulation in men with uncontrolled systemic arterial hypertension residing in rural areas.

2. METHODS AND MATERIALS

This is a cross-sectional study in which the sample was divided into groups. Following the classification of physical activity levels by the International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ), two groups were formed: Active Hypertensives and Sedentary Hypertensives. The research was conducted at Basic Health Units (UBS) in the rural area of the Maranhão.

2.1 SAMPLE

Using criteria and statistical calculations estimated by the power analysis method via G*power software, tests from the T family were considered, specifically an effect size of 0.8, a confidence interval of 0.95, and a probabilistic error of 0.05, distributed across two groups.

Thus, the statistical test applied was the independent samples t-test, indicating an ideal total sample size of 70 individuals subdivided into two groups. Considering a potential sample loss of 20%, the ideal total sample size should be adjusted to 84 individuals. However, it was not possible to achieve the ideal number of volunteers. The groups were composed of active and sedentary uncontrolled hypertensive individuals who met the inclusion criteria. To select the sample, we contacted teams from several UBS in rural Pinheiro, Maranhão, and requested that they identify hypertensive individuals to participate in the research. These individuals were invited to participate and agreed to do so. Therefore, the sample was non-probabilistic, with randomization into two groups.

2.1.1 Inclusion Criteria: Male hypertensive individuals with uncontrolled hypertension, who have the cognitive ability to understand the research process, sign the informed consent form, and voluntarily agree to participate in the study were included.

2.1.2 Non-inclusion Criteria: Individuals with communication limitations that prevented the application of questionnaires were not included in this study. Hypertensive individuals with controlled and stable blood pressure were also excluded, as well as those lacking the cognitive ability to understand the research process and sign the informed consent form.

2.1.3 Exclusion Criteria: Volunteers who reported not completing all evaluations on the day of data collection or who withdrew during the data collection process were excluded.

2.2 Physical and Clinical Assessment

The volunteers underwent a sequence of anamnesis, answered the IPAQ questionnaire, had their blood pressure measured and underwent an electrocardiogram exam. *Anamnesis*

The selected individuals were informed about the risks and benefits of the research and, upon agreeing, signed the Informed Consent Form. Subsequently, they answered a questionnaire for sample characterization, which included information on personal characteristics, sociodemographic and socioeconomic data, as well as current health history.

2.2.1 Anthropometric Evaluation: Weight measurement was performed using a digital scale on the kilogram scale (Balmak, BK – 50FAN, São Paulo). For stature, the EST 23 Trena Compact Stadiometer was used in the millimeter scale. Also, the body mass index (BMI) identified in the weight (Kg)/height (m²) formula.

2.2.2 Blood Pressure Measurements: The procedures for the measurement of Blood Pressure (BP) were made according to the guidelines of The Seventh Report of the Joint National Committee on Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure (JNC7). In summary, patients remained in the sitting position in a comfortable chair for 20 min. With an automatic and noninvasive BP monitor (BP710, Omron, Tokyo, Japan), three measurements of BP were performed on the right arm, with at least a 2-min interval between each one.

2.2.3 International Physical Activity Questionnaire (IPAQ): To assess the participants level of physical activity, the short version of the IPAQ was administered. The classification was conducted as follows: active individuals were those who engaged in vigorous activity for ≥ 3 days/week and ≥ 20 minutes per session, or moderate activity or walking for ≥ 5 days/week and ≥ 30 minutes per session, or any combination of activities totaling ≥ 5 days/week and ≥ 150 minutes/week (walking + moderate + vigorous). Irregularly active individuals were those who engaged in physical activity but insufficiently to be classified as active, as they did not meet the recommendations for frequency or duration.

2.2.4 Heart Rate Variability (HRV): To extract signals to HRV was realized an electrocardiogram 12-leads utilizing the device micromed wincardio (Micromed –WinCardio, v. 6.1.1 software) to obtain R-R intervals. The exam was realized in a silent room; the patient was instructed not to speak during exam and remain the supine position during 10 minutes while the exam as performed. After exam the intervals R-R series were extrated in format txt using software wincardio, HRV indices were analyzed using Kubios HRV software, version 3.2 (Biosignal Analysis and Medical Imaging Group, Kuopio, Finland). The software converts signals R-R to digital electrocardiogram in variables to examine autonomic nervous system function.

All dates were disposable after correct about filter artefacts and were used SDNN (standard deviation of RR intervals) and RMSSD (Root mean square of successive RR intervals differences) in the time-domain. In frequency-domain were utilized low frequency (LF ms^2) (LF nu-normalized) and high frequency (HF ms^2) (HF nu-normalized) bands in milliseconds and percentage, that represents predominantly sympathetic and parasympathetic modulation, respectively, and LF/HF ratio as representative vagal sympathetic balance (Rodrigues et al., 2013).

The nonlinear index used was SD1 (ms), and SD2 (ms). The Stress index is the square root (to make the index normally distributed) of the Baevsky's stress index . The values of Baevsky's Stress Index between 50-150 are considered normal, 150-500 elevated, 500-900 high, and >900 very high (Standard & Premium, 2018).

2.2.5 Laboratory Tests: Samples of whole blood sample and serum were collected at baseline and after twelve weeks of exercise protocol, by a technician or nurse on duty in the laboratory of the Universidade Federal do Maranhão (UFMA). The patients were instructed to remain at 12 hours of fasting before laboratory evaluations. On this same day, the other protocols of the study were not performed so that there was no interference in the results and for greater comfort of the participants.

Posteriorly, the samples were taken for automating analysis in ADVIA 2120i Hematology System and ADVIA 2400 Clinical Chemistry System (Siemens Healthcare Diagnostics, Forchheim), where the following parameters were evaluated: concentrations of in whole blood sample and serum levels of urea (mg/dL), creatinine (mg/dL), HDL cholesterol, total cholesterol, Triglycerides (mg/dl), Proteins (mg/dl), Urea (mg/dl) and Uric acid (mg/dl).

2.3 Ethical Aspects

The present study is part of a larger umbrella project titled: Effects of aerobic training on cardiorenal adaptations and cardiac autonomic modulation in hypertensive individuals, which was submitted on 07/21/2020 at 11:32 a.m. to the Ethics Committee and approved under opinion number: 4.284.220. The research will adhere to the ethical principles governing research involving human subjects and will comply with the guidelines of Resolution 466/12 of the National Health Council (CNS).

2.4 Statistical Analysis

All data were presented in mean and standard deviation. The Shapiro-Wilk test was applied to verify the normality of the data. The parameters of interest were analyzed using unpaired Student's t-test or Mann-Whitney U test depending on normality.

Pearson's and Spearman's correlations were verified on the variables. The results were considered statistically significant for the value $p < 0.05$. For data analysis, GraphPad Prism version 8.0.0 for Mac OSx, GraphPad Software, San Diego, California, U.S.A., www.graphpad.com was used.

3. RESULTS

Table 1: Characterization of hemodynamic and anthropometric variables of uncontrolled hypertensive men from rural areas.

Variables	Active Group (n = 9)	Sedentary Group (n = 7)	p-value
SBP (mmHg)	139.33 ± 15.92	147.86 ± 38.40	0.55
DBP (mmHg)	84.56 ± 7.98	85.57 ± 11.34	0.83
HR (bpm)	72.78 ± 10.81	74.86 ± 17.45	0.77
Age (years)	67.33 ± 13.62	68.57 ± 15.34	0.86
Height (m)	1.62 ± 0.09	1.64 ± 0.06	0.64
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.46 ± 3.51	25.71 ± 4.06	0.52
Abdominal Circumference(cm)	91.94 ± 9.37	96.07 ± 8.54	0.38

SBP: Systolic Blood Pressure; **DBP:** Diastolic Blood Pressure; **HR:** Heart Rate; **BMI:** Body Mass Index; Unpaired t-test, significance level $p < 0.05$.

Table 1 presents the characterization of hemodynamic and anthropometric variables of uncontrolled hypertensive men from rural areas. The statistical analysis did not show differences between the active and sedentary groups in variables such as systolic and diastolic blood pressure, heart rate, age, height, body mass index, and abdominal circumference.

Table 2: Cardiac autonomic modulation of uncontrolled hypertensive men from rural areas

Variables	Active Group (n = 9)	Sedentary Group (n = 7)	p-value
Time Domain			
RR (ms)	843.44 ± 121.00	839.29 ± 204.43	0.96
SDNN (ms)	36.52 ± 25.55	13.19 ± 7.80	0.03
RMSSD (ms)	47.43 ± 40.94	14.46 ± 8.49	0.05
Frequency Domain			
LF (ms ²)	438.00 ± 317.29	84.14 ± 134.84	0.01
HF (ms ²)	717.00 ± 768.99	95.71 ± 135.62	0.05
LF (nu)	43.82 ± 10.18	45.29 ± 21.33	0.85
LF (nu)	55.72 ± 10.04	47.27 ± 12.42	0.15
LF/HF	0.83 ± 0.32	1.24 ± 0.58	0.09
Nonlinear			
SD1(ms)	33.53 ± 29.00	11.43 ± 7.01	0.07
SD2(ms)	38.50 ± 22.75	11.08 ± 11.02	0.01
Cardiovascular Stress			
Stress Index	11.10 ± 3.16	25.43 ± 17.13	0.02

Unpaired t-test, significance level $p < 0.05$.

Table 2 presents the cardiac autonomic modulation of active and sedentary uncontrolled hypertensive men. After data analysis, significant differences were observed in the SDNN indices, indicating greater heart rate variability in the active group compared to the sedentary group. This behavior is also confirmed by the SD2 index from the nonlinear analysis. These indicators of cardiac autonomic modulation are further supported by a reduction in cardiovascular risk, as demonstrated by the cardiovascular stress index, with the active group showing lower cardiovascular stress compared to the sedentary group. The active group exhibited greater parasympathetic cardiac modulation compared to the sedentary group, as demonstrated by the LF (ms²) index; however, this behavior was not confirmed in the normalized LF (nu) index.

The other indices analyzed in the time domain (RR, RMSSD), heart rate frequency domain (HF (ms²), LF (nu), HF (nu), and LF/HF), and the nonlinear SD1 (ms) did not show significant differences.

Table 3: Biochemical analysis of uncontrolled hypertensive men from rural areas

Variables	Clinical Reference	Active Group (n = 9)	Sedentary Group (n = 7)	p-value
Creatinine (mg/dl)	0.5 a 1.3	1.28 ± 0.30	2.06 ± 1.49.43	0.14
Urea (mg/dl)	20 a 50	33.11 ± 9.41	35.71 ± 9.69	0.57
Uric Acid (mg/dl)	2.5 a 7.0	5.85 ± 1.25	5.10 ± 1.55	0.71
Proteins (g/dl)	6 a 8	7.10 ± 0.67	7.30 ± 0.48	0.61
Triglycerides (mg/dl)	> 175	150.56 ± 104.95	128.86 ± 44.49	0.59
Total Cholesterol (mg/dl)	< 190	164.78 ± 31.95	158.43 ± 35.83	0.52
HDL Cholesterol (mg/dl)	>40	38.89 ± 10.58	36.29 ± 6.42	0.68

Unpaired t-test, significance level $p < 0.05$

Table 3 presents the comparison of biochemical variables of active and sedentary uncontrolled hypertensive men. Statistical analysis revealed no significant differences in creatinine (mg/dl), urea (mg/dl), uric acid (mg/dl), proteins (g/dl), triglycerides (mg/dl), total cholesterol (mg/dl), and HDL cholesterol (mg/dl).

Figure 1: (A) Negative correlation between SDNN and the stress index in uncontrolled hypertensive individuals. (B) Positive correlation between abdominal circumference and diastolic blood pressure in uncontrolled hypertensive individuals

Figure 1 presents the Pearson correlation between the variables SDNN and the stress index in uncontrolled hypertensive individuals (graph A). This correlation was negative and moderate, indicating that greater heart rate variability, as observed in SDNN, corresponds to lower cardiovascular stress. In graph B, a positive and moderate Pearson correlation is observed between abdominal circumference and diastolic blood pressure, demonstrating that an increase in abdominal circumference corresponds to higher diastolic blood pressure values.

4. DISCUSSION

This study aimed to evaluate the level of physical activity and cardiac autonomic modulation in men with uncontrolled systemic arterial hypertension from rural areas. Our main findings indicate greater heart rate variability and lower cardiovascular stress in the active group compared to the sedentary group. Additionally, we identified a moderate negative correlation, suggesting that higher heart rate variability, as observed in the SDNN, is associated with lower cardiovascular stress, and a moderate positive correlation between abdominal circumference and diastolic blood pressure, demonstrating that an increase in abdominal circumference corresponds to higher diastolic blood pressure values (central figure).

Regarding the greater heart rate variability observed in active hypertensive individuals in our study, this behavior was also demonstrated in the study by Nakayama (2020), which evaluated the effect of increased physical activity on high-frequency (HRV) heart rate variability (HF) during the first hour after the onset of sleep in patients with hypertension and/or stable angina pectoris. The increase in the HF index may have been due to the increase in physical activity. An increase in physical activity suggests that sleep quality at the beginning of the sleep cycle may be improved, which could affect the patient's prognosis (Nakayama et al., 2020).

Furthermore, attention should be given to the optimal time of day for performing daily physical activity, as demonstrated in the study by Nakayama (2022), which investigated whether morning or afternoon activity is more effective in increasing the high-frequency index. The study concluded that afternoon physical exercise may improve the prognosis of patients with cardiovascular diseases, not only by preventing excessive blood pressure, afterload, and sympathetic tone but also by positively influencing the parasympathetic system and sleep. Thus, it is known that increased parasympathetic cardiac modulation may reduce cardiovascular risk factors in hypertensive patients (Nakayama et al., 2022).

Regarding physical activity and increased HRV, these factors may be associated with reduced sitting time and improved sleep quality in patients with increased cardiovascular risk. Reducing continuous sitting time during the day may partially contribute to improving the prognosis of patients with cardiovascular risk factors, not only by preventing muscle loss but also by positively influencing parasympathetic tone during sleep (Nakayama et al., 2021). Similarly, sarcopenia is independently associated with lower heart rate variability, which may be influenced by a more sedentary lifestyle, leading to reduced parasympathetic autonomic modulation (Zheng et al., 2024).

Still regarding the behavior of lower cardiovascular stress in active hypertensive individuals demonstrated in our study, this may reflect bodily stress and recovery reactions measured by devices that assess heart rate (HR) and its variability (HRV). The study by Seipäjärvi et al. (2022) evaluated how psychosocial stress affects physiological and psychological responses to stress in healthy young individuals (18–30 years), middle-aged individuals (45–64 years), and patients with hypertension and/or previous evidence of prediabetes or type 2 diabetes. The study concluded that an HRV-based stress index can be used to quantify physiological responses to psychosocial stress across various health and age groups (Seipäjärvi et al., 2022). Thus, it is understood that factors increasing cardiovascular risk, such as poor sleep quality, sedentary behavior, and cardiometabolic syndrome, are well-studied and have been shown to reduce heart rate variability (Gauche et al., 2017; Mamatha, Ramachandra, & Smitha, 2019; Siaplaouras et al., 2021). Conversely, maintaining an active lifestyle reduces the manifestation of adverse cardiovascular effects (Chaiduang, Klinsophon, Wattanapanyawech, & Therapies, 2024; Kadoya et al., 2015).

Moreover, risk factors such as abdominal obesity and cardiovascular stress can impair health and increase the risk of adverse cardiovascular events. As observed in our study, a negative correlation was identified between higher heart rate variability and lower

cardiovascular stress. Similarly, increased abdominal obesity showed a positive correlation with diastolic blood pressure. As observed in a review study that evaluated various other studies involving physical activity and HRV in adults with overweight or obesity, with or without comorbidities, a negative relationship between moderate to vigorous physical activity and HRV indices was found in two studies. There was also a negative relationship between sedentary time and HF ($p = 0.049$) and LF/HF ($p = 0.036$), as well as a positive relationship between sedentary time and LF ($p = 0.014$). Additionally, a dose-response association was identified between vigorous exercise and higher SDNN, LF power, and HF power in one of the studies (Sinha, Vaishali, Maiya, Shivashankar, & Shashikiran, 2023).

Furthermore, we must consider the impact of an active level of physical activity on cardiometabolic responses, particularly in protecting against and reducing cardiovascular risks (Banerjee, Singh, Raju, Gupta, & Care, 2022; Oliveira et al., 2020). Regarding the responses of cardiac autonomic modulation, physical activity not only increases heart rate variability but also enhances parasympathetic modulation (Yadav et al., 2017). It is well known that obese individuals have a higher prevalence of cardiovascular diseases, which are presumably caused by autonomic dysfunction and/or metabolic disorders. Changes in cardiac autonomic functions highlight alterations in heart rate variability (HRV) indicators (Gandhi, Sorte, Chatur, & Rathod, 2024; Yadav et al., 2017). On the other hand, maintaining an active lifestyle has shown a significant effect in reducing blood glucose levels and improving HRV (Hoffmann et al., 2024).

Thus, the sympathovagal imbalance already appears to contribute to elevated diastolic blood pressure in young individuals (Köchli, Schutte, & Kruger, 2020). However, studies also show an increase in HRV and VO_2 in obese individuals following physical training (Jabbour & Iancu, 2021) or a healthy lifestyle (Liao et al., 2017). These adaptations are fundamental for the body to enhance safety and reduce adverse cardiovascular effects.

Our study has some limitations, such as a small sample size, the lack of detailed information about the types of medications taken by the participants, and the absence of a more direct method to measure physical activity levels, such as accelerometers. However, it highlights the significant relevance of preliminarily evaluating the lifestyle of these hypertensive men from rural areas and assessing their cardiovascular risks.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on findings it is concluded that active hypertensive men exhibit greater heart rate variability and lower cardiovascular stress compared to sedentary individuals. Additionally, we identified a moderate negative correlation, indicating that higher heart rate variability, as observed in the SDNN, is associated with lower cardiovascular stress. A moderate positive correlation was also observed between abdominal circumference and diastolic blood pressure, demonstrating that an increase in abdominal circumference corresponds to higher diastolic blood pressure values.

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